

THE WAY AND MOTIVATION FOR FUTURE DOCTORS IN DISTANCE EDUCATION**Moroz P.,***PhD, Associate Professor, Chernivtsi, Ukraine,
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Scientific and technological progress, which has covered all areas of medicine, encourages not only the active introduction of new technologies in the treatment process, but also the development of new science-intensive technologies for diagnosis, treatment of patients and prevention of various complications.

Keywords: group activity, surgery, study, high educational institution, medicine.

The staff of the Department of Surgery №1 BSMU for many years is the locomotive of scientific and technological progress in surgery in Bukovina. The Clinic of the Department of Surgery is a regional methodological center for providing surgical care to the population of Chernivtsi region. The base of the clinic is the Department of General, Thoracic, Vascular Surgery and Proctology of Chernivtsi Regional Clinical Hospital, which encourages a wide range of scientific, technical and technological research. The clinic of the department performs a wide range of modern surgical interventions on the esophagus, digestive organs, lungs, rectum, blood vessels, developed methods of diagnosis, surgical and conservative treatment and prevention of postoperative complications. Employees of the department were the first in Bukovyna, back in 1996, to perform laparoscopic surgery in planned and emergency surgery, and in 2020 performed hemicolostomy.

In 2011, the Regional Center for Minimally Invasive Surgery and Gynecology was established on the basis of the Department of Surgery and departments of the regional clinical hospital. The task of the Center was to more widely introduce into the treatment process methods of laparoscopic and thoracoscopic surgical interventions, development of new and improvement of existing methods of operations. The Center has implemented laparoscopic operations for acute appendicitis, acute and chronic cholecystitis, inguinal and femoral hernias, hernia of the esophageal orifice of the diaphragm, esophagus, with some complications of peptic ulcer disease, conjunctival disease, thorax, pleura, thymus, Raynaud's disease, performed transthoracic neurophrenicotomy developed by the staff of the department. With the involvement of gynecologists, surgical interventions are performed for infertility, ovarian cysts, salpingitis, ectopic pregnancy, uterine fibroids. Laparoscopic interventions in emergency surgery have

been introduced - appendectomies, viscerolysis, autopsy and rehabilitation of delimited peritoneal abscesses are performed. These operations are performed mainly by employees of the department. The Center for Minimally Invasive Surgery and Gynecology trains doctors at the postgraduate stage of training, provides consulting and methodological assistance to medical institutions of the region.

In recent years, the staff of the department is actively conducting research to study the influence of genetically determined factors on the course of acute surgical diseases of the abdominal cavity. This latest scientific direction allows not only to reveal new links in the pathogenesis of acute surgical diseases (peritonitis, pancreatitis, intestinal obstruction), but also to develop highly informative methods for predicting the development and features of these diseases. This radically changes not only the existing criteria for their diagnosis, but also the principles of treatment tactics - conservative therapy and surgical interventions aimed at improving the results of treatment and prevention of postoperative complications. Limited high-cost technological equipment of the clinic encouraged the staff to develop science-intensive low-cost and low-cost technologies for surgical interventions, which allow existing means to ensure higher reliability of various stages of the operation, reduce the risk of complications, achieve high treatment results. Among such methods are new types of intestinal sutures, methods of fixing and protecting the line of anastomoses, intubation of the intestine, local supply of drugs, sanitation of the peritoneal cavity, etc. All these methods are protected by patents and implemented far beyond Bukovina. One of the priority scientific and practical directions of the Department of Surgery is the development of methods for early diagnosis and effective treatment of various

forms of peritonitis. Employees of the department proposed new informative methods for diagnosing acute peritonitis and its complications, developed effective methods of surgical interventions, which are protected by patents and used far beyond Ukraine. Recognition of the priorities of scientists on this issue is evidenced by their numerous speeches at scientific congresses in Austria, Moldova, Russia, Poland, publications in the United States, Canada, Israel, Germany, Portugal, Spain and others. The staff of the department published 5 monographs on this topic, defended 5 doctoral and 14 candidate dissertations, received more than 40 A patents and copyright certificates for inventions, held numerous conferences, symposia and congresses. Since the founding of the department, one of the leading areas of its scientific and practical activities has been the study of various aspects of endemic goiter in Bukovina and the development of effective methods of treatment. Until now, the department remains the only scientific and practical center in Bukovina for surgical treatment of thyroid diseases. The vast majority of employees of the department are surgeons of the highest category, who are constantly on duty in the departments of the hospital, regional sanitary aviation, often go to the areas of the region, where they implement the developed methods. In the thoracic department, thoracoscopic operations are performed for various diseases of the lungs, pleura and interstitium. Technological innovations - colonoscopic surgical interventions, electric welding of tissues, methods of diagnosis and treatment of nonspecific ulcerative colitis and Crohn's disease - are widely used in the proctology department. The department has an active student research group, where students of different courses not only learn the skills of surgical manipulations, surgical interventions, but also learn from the experience of their mentors and conduct clinical and experimental research. With their scientific achievements, the group members speak at conferences of various levels, including international ones. They are winners of many competitions and congresses. Considerable attention is paid to the training of students and young surgeons. 8 textbooks have been published, a computer test program on surgery has been developed.

The latest technologies are widely used in the educational process - live broadcasts of operations from the operating room to the classroom, own, videos, simulators, computer programs. The department is a base for training interns in the specialty "Surgery". Since 2001, the department conducts pre-certification training and internship cycles for surgeons, thematic improvement courses in minimally invasive surgery, proctology, vascular and thoracic surgery. More than 550 doctors were involved in postgraduate studies.

The staff of the Department of Surgery not only preserves and multiplies the traditions laid down at the founding of the department, but also forms new, promising areas of activity aimed at implementing the latest teaching technologies, scientific substantiation of diagnosis and effective treatment of patients, development of new technologies.

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